

Finite size effects on elastic scattering

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1 Formal Derivation

1.1 Basic definitions

Define $\rho_\infty(\mathbf{r})$ as the (scattering length) density distribution of a perfect monoatomic crystal of infinite extension. Without loss of generality, we take the origin of the coordinate axis as the position of the lattice coordinate indexed by the triplet $(a, b, c) = (0, 0, 0)$. Therefore, we have:

$$\rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{a,b,c \in \mathbb{Z}} \delta(\mathbf{r} - a\mathbf{a} - b\mathbf{b} - c\mathbf{c}) \quad (1)$$

for generic crystal unit vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$. Define the indicator function $\chi_\Sigma(\mathbf{r})$ of a compact region $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{R}^3$:

$$\chi_\Sigma(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mathbf{r} \in \Sigma \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \quad (2)$$

Its center of mass \mathbf{r}_Σ is given by:

$$\mathbf{r}_\Sigma = \frac{1}{|\Sigma|} \int d^3r r \chi_\Sigma(\mathbf{r}). \quad (3)$$

Here, $|\Sigma|$ is the volume of the region Σ . Similarly, we can define a rotation matrix \mathbb{M}_R that relates the region Σ to a reference Σ_0 centered at the origin and oriented in some standard way with respect to the coordinate axes. We can thus write

$$\chi_\Sigma(\mathbf{r}) = \chi_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M}_R(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_\Sigma)). \quad (4)$$

Finally, define $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ as

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) \equiv \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}) \chi_\Sigma(\mathbf{r}). \quad (5)$$

$\rho(\mathbf{r})$ can be intended as a finite-size sample of the density distribution ρ_∞ .

If a monochromatic and plane EM wave is scattered elastically by the sample ρ , the scattered intensity $I(\mathbf{q})$ at momentum transfer vector \mathbf{q} is proportional to the square modulus of the 3-D Fourier transform of ρ :

$$\begin{aligned} I(\mathbf{q}) &= |\mathcal{F}_{3D}[\rho](\mathbf{q})|^2 \\ &= \left| \int d^3r \rho(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\mathbf{q}\cdot\mathbf{r}} \right|^2 \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{3D}[K(\mathbf{r})](\mathbf{q}) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$K(\mathbf{r}) = \rho(\mathbf{r}) * \rho(-\mathbf{r})$ is the density autocorrelation function of the sample and the last equality in Equation 6 follows from the convolution theorem. Explicitly,

$K(\mathbf{r})$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} K(\mathbf{r}) &= \int d^3r' \chi_{\Sigma}(\mathbf{r}') \chi_{\Sigma}(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}) \rho_{\infty}(\mathbf{r}') \rho_{\infty}(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}) \\ &= \int_{\Sigma'(\mathbf{r})} d^3r' \rho_{\infty}(\mathbf{r}') \rho_{\infty}(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\Sigma'(\mathbf{r})$ is the intersection of Σ with its copy translated by \mathbf{r} . This implies $|\Sigma'| \leq |\Sigma|$, with the equality holding at $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}$.

1.2 The limiting behaviour for large size

Let us first consider a sequence of compact regions $\{\Sigma_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ satisfying $\{\forall R \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}, \exists k^* \in \mathbb{N} : \forall k > k^*, B(R) \subset \Sigma_k\}$, where $B(R)$ is the sphere of radius R centered at the origin. In other words, consider a sequence of larger and larger samples Σ_k of ρ^{∞} . As $|\Sigma|$ diverges, we expect the intensity I to grow proportionally and therefore the ratio $I/|\Sigma|$ to tend to a well-defined limit I_{∞} :

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\infty}(\mathbf{q}) &= \lim_{|\Sigma| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{|\Sigma|} \mathcal{F}_{3D}[K](\mathbf{q}) \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{3D} \left[\lim_{|\Sigma| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K}{|\Sigma|} \right] (\mathbf{q}) \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{3D}[K_{\infty}](\mathbf{q}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Here, we have defined the limiting autocorrelation function $K_{\infty}(\mathbf{r})$. The exchange of limit and Fourier transformation is justified by the Wiener-Kinchin theorem. Note that convergence must be intended in the sense appropriate for tempered distributions. In particular, since ρ_{∞} is a 3-D periodic array of δ

functions, so are $I_\infty(\mathbf{q})$ and $K_\infty(\mathbf{r})$. Explicitly, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
K_\infty(\mathbf{r}) &= \lim_{|\Sigma| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K(\mathbf{r})}{|\Sigma|} \\
&= \lim_{|\Sigma| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{|\Sigma|} \int_{\Sigma'(\mathbf{r})} d^3r' \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}') \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}) \\
&= \lim_{|\Sigma| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|\Sigma'|(\mathbf{r})}{|\Sigma|} \overline{\rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}') \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r})}_{\Sigma'} \\
&= \overline{\rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}') \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r})}_{V_{hkl}}
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The third equality follows from the mean value theorem. The last passage uses the fact that $\forall \mathbf{r}, |\Sigma'|(\mathbf{r})/|\Sigma| \rightarrow 1$ and the periodicity of $\rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}') \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r})$ to perform the average only in the volume V_{hkl} of an arbitrary unit cell.

1.3 Random sampling

In general, predicting the scattered intensity of a specific finite-sized sample requires calculating the Fourier transform of ρ directly via Equation 6. However, if we can assume that the sampling process that generates particles is somewhat uncorrelated with the underlying density distribution, the math simplifies considerably. More precisely, the definition of K (Equation 7) and Equation 4 imply

$$\begin{aligned}
K(\mathbf{r}) &= K(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_\Sigma, \mathbb{M}) \\
&= \int d^3r' \chi_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M}\mathbf{r}') \chi_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M}(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r})) \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}_\Sigma) \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}_\Sigma - \mathbf{r})
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

For each \mathbf{r} , we can then consider the expected value of the autocorrelation $\bar{K}(\mathbf{r})$ over the probability distribution describing the possible positions of the center

of mass \mathbf{r}_Σ . By assuming the probability to be uniform over a region $V \subset \mathbb{R}^3$

and taking the limit $|V| \rightarrow \infty$ in the fashion of Equation 8 we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{K}(\mathbf{r}; \mathbb{M}) &\equiv \lim_{|V| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{|V|} \int_V d^3 r_\Sigma K(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_\Sigma, \mathbb{M}) \\
&= \lim_{|V| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{|V|} \int d^3 r' \chi_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M} \mathbf{r}') \chi_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M}(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r})) \int_V d^3 r_\Sigma \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}_\Sigma) \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}_\Sigma - \mathbf{r}) \\
&= \int d^3 r' \chi_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M} \mathbf{r}') \chi_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M}(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r})) \lim_{|V| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{|V|} \int_V d^3 r_\Sigma \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}_\Sigma) \rho_\infty(\mathbf{r}' + \mathbf{r}_\Sigma - \mathbf{r}) \\
&= |\Sigma'_0| \left(\mathbb{M} \mathbf{r} \right) K_\infty(\mathbf{r}) = |\Sigma_0| W_{\Sigma_0} \left(\mathbb{M} \mathbf{r} \right) K_\infty(\mathbf{r})
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Here, we have exploited the fact that K_∞ only depends on \mathbf{r} and defined the normalized autocorrelation function W_{Σ_0} of the “window” Σ_0 :

$$W_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{|\Sigma'_0|(\mathbf{r})}{|\Sigma_0|}. \tag{12}$$

By application of the convolution theorem, the corresponding average scattered intensity $\bar{I}(\mathbf{q}) = \mathcal{F}_{3D}[\bar{K}](\mathbf{q})$ is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{I}(\mathbf{q}) &= (2\pi)^{-3} |\Sigma_0| \left(\mathcal{F}_{3D}[W_{\Sigma_0}](\mathbb{M}^{-1} \mathbf{q}) * I_\infty(\mathbf{q}) \right), \\
&= |\Sigma_0| \left(w_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbb{M}^{-1} \mathbf{q}) * I_\infty(\mathbf{q}) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where $w_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbf{q}) = (2\pi)^{-3} \mathcal{F}_{3D}[W_{\Sigma_0}](\mathbf{q})$ is the \mathbf{q} -normalized “smearing” function unique to the shape Σ_0 . In order to check normalization, note that the integral of w_{Σ_0} over all \mathbf{q} is simply $W_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbf{0}) = 1$ due to the inversion theorem.

The problem of calculating the finite size effects on the scattered intensity of

samples of ρ^∞ is therefore reduced to the calculation of a convolution between two independent functions which encode the properties of the shape and of the underlying crystalline density distribution, respectively. Similar conclusions are drawn in the classic book by Hosemann[1], although the present formalism is significantly more agile. While these results are exact under the assumption of uniform sampling stated above, it is only an approximation if the sampling process for particles of shape Σ_0 is strongly correlated with ρ^∞ ; for example, this can occur if the atoms in clusters of shape Σ_0 are forced to lie in specific positions with respect to the coordinate system of Σ_0 . Even in these cases, however, this formula provides a convenient approximation to the exact Equation 6.

For each fixed shape Σ_0 , two types of orientational averages can be performed by integrating Equation 13. The first is over all possible orientations of the shape Σ with respect to the underlying crystal lattice (represented by \mathbb{M}); this operation makes $w_{\Sigma_0}(\mathbf{q})$ depend only on the magnitude of the wavevector $q = |\mathbf{q}|$. The other is over all possible orientations of the lattice with respect to the laboratory reference frame.

1.4 Finite size in one dimension

In one dimension, the average scattered intensity at wave vector q generated by uniform sampling of the one-dimensional distribution $\rho_\infty(x) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta(x - nL_0)$ in windows of length L is

$$\bar{I}(q) = L (I_\infty(q) * w_L(q)). \quad (14)$$

The limiting autocorrelation K_∞ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
K_\infty(x) &= \frac{1}{L_0} \int_{-\frac{L_0}{2}}^{\frac{L_0}{2}} dx' \rho_\infty(x') \rho_\infty(x' - x) \\
&= \frac{1}{L_0} \int_{-\frac{L_0}{2}}^{\frac{L_0}{2}} dx' \sum_{n,n'} \delta(x' - nL_0) \delta(x' - x - n'L_0) \\
&= \frac{1}{L_0} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta(x - nL_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

The intensity I_∞ is then

$$\begin{aligned}
I_\infty(q) &= \mathcal{F}_{1D}[K_\infty](q) \\
&= \frac{2\pi}{L_0^2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \delta\left(q - \frac{2\pi n}{L_0}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Finally, the smearing function $w_L(q)$ for such windowing process is

$$\begin{aligned}
w_L(q) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \mathcal{F}_{1D}[W_L](q) \\
&= \frac{1}{2\pi L} |\mathcal{F}_{1D}[\chi_L]|^2(q) \\
&= \frac{L}{2\pi} \text{sinc}^2\left(\frac{qL}{2}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

References

- (1) Hosemann, R.; Bagchi, S., *Direct Analysis of Diffraction by Matter*; North Holland, Amsterdam (1962).